

The Legal Dimensions of Cyber Stalking in India: An Analytical Study

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Abstract

A new type of crime is emerging in cyberspace, when a person repeatedly attempts to get in touch with another, creating a sense of menace in the other person's head. People refer to this new crime as "internet stalking." Cyberstalking is characterised as a criminal act in which stalkers utilise the internet or any other electronic gadget to follow a target. Cyberstalking is often associated with online abuse and harassment. It entails continuously intimidating or harassing a specific person. There are several ways to stalk someone, including following them to their house or place of business, damaging their belongings, leaving notes or items behind, or engaging in persistent harassment. Cyberstalkers constantly believe they can hide and remain anonymous. Stated differently, the primary advantage of a cyberstalker is that they may rely on the anonymity that the internet affords them, enabling them to monitor their victim's activities without having to reveal their identity. Therefore, effective cyber tools are required to investigate cybercrimes, be ready to protect against them, and prosecute victims. The term "cyberstalking" refers to the criminal activity of a stalker using social media and other online networks to conduct illegal and unlawful monitoring. Stalking is defined as unwelcome and/or persistent observation of another person by an individual or group under section 354D of the IPC. The term "stalking" alone denotes illegitimacy, which makes it a terrible crime. As such, cyberstalking automatically qualifies as a serious offence. The word "cyber" refers to anything having to do with computers or computer networks, such as the internet, but the phrase "stalking" relates to the unlawful act of watching someone. This word doesn't convey a really novel idea. Both the idea and the practise of online interaction and communication emerged as the field of interaction and communication advanced.

Key words : Cyberspace, Identity Theft, Harassment, Anonymity and Psychological Suffering.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

A new type of crime is emerging in cyberspace, when a person repeatedly attempts to get in touch with another, creating a sense of menace in the other person's head. People refer to this new crime as "internet stalking." Cyberstalking is characterised as a criminal act in which stalkers utilise the internet or any other electronic gadget to follow a target. Cyberstalking is often associated with online abuse and harassment. It entails continuously intimidating or harassing a specific person. There are several ways to stalk someone, including following them to their house or place of business, damaging their belongings, leaving notes or items behind, or engaging in persistent harassment. Cyberstalkers constantly believe they can hide and remain anonymous. Stated differently, the primary advantage of a cyberstalker is that they may rely on the anonymity that the internet affords them, enabling them to monitor their victim's activities without having to reveal their identity. Therefore, effective cyber tools are required to investigate cybercrimes, be ready to protect against them, and prosecute victims.

The term "cyberstalking" refers to the criminal activity of a stalker using social media and other online networks to conduct illegal and unlawful monitoring. Stalking is defined as unwelcome and/or

persistent observation of another person by an individual or group under section 354D of the IPC. It frequently has to do with intimidating and harassing the victim, and it could involve spying on them and physically pursuing them. The term "stalking" alone denotes illegitimacy, which makes it a terrible crime. As such, cyberstalking automatically qualifies as a serious offence. The word "cyber" refers to anything having to do with computers or computer networks, such as the internet, but the phrase "stalking" relates to the unlawful act of watching someone. This word doesn't convey a really novel idea. Both the idea and the practise of online interaction and communication emerged as the field of interaction and communication advanced.

1.2 Meaning of Cyber Stalking

"The act of a stalker using the internet to pursue their target is known as cyberstalking." In order to comprehend this phrase more fully, we must first comprehend how this crime is performed online, as we have previously discussed in the preceding topic. Cyberstalking is often associated with sexual harassment alone through the internet, but, as with physical stalking, it can take many different forms, such as identity theft, blackmail, bullying, and false allegations. This essay will concentrate on the aspects of cyberstalking that involve false charges, harassment, and blackmail. Cyberstalking is the practise of monitoring an individual's social media activity by posting offensive comments, sending unsolicited sexual or abusive emails, tracking a person's shopping habits, and generally using any means at hand to keep tabs on the victim. The anonymity of the internet contributes to this, making it more difficult to track the victim and easier for the criminal to commit the crime because it disguises the user's location. The victim and the offender may even be on different sides of the world. Additionally, new technology and software makes it even more difficult to track the person because they may be right next door, but their location can be revealed in. Since we rely on the internet for everything these days, even the most basic tasks can be completed with it. As a result, cyberstalking is a very serious threat that needs to be taken seriously. If cyberstalking is not handled with the necessary seriousness, it could escalate to dangerous new heights in the future.

1.3 Types of Cyber Stalking

- **E-mail stalking:** This email correspondence is direct. which is the harassment form that is most readily available. In some ways, it resembles conventional stalking quite a bit. One can harass others by sending spam or viruses, or they can send threatening, hateful, or vulgar emails. For instance, two MBA students intimidated a female classmate in India in 2004 by sending her emails. For stalkers looking to more effectively hide their traces, the free availability of anonymizers and anonymous remailers – which obscure the sender's name and the content of the email – offers a high level of security.
- **Internet stalking:** Through the Internet, communication is possible anywhere. Compared to email stalking, this domain is more expansive and visible to the public. Here, stalkers have a plethora of options for tormenting their targets. For instance, a woman endured six months of stalking. Her harasser uploaded notes in a chat room threatening to kill her and torment her, along with altered sexual images of her that included personal information.
- **Computer stalking:** This is using someone else's computer without their permission. In this kind of stalking, the stalker takes advantage of the way the Windows operating system and the Internet function to take control of the targeted victim's computer. Here, as soon as the target computer makes any kind of Internet connection, the cyberstalker can speak with them directly. The victim's sole line of defence is to disconnect and give up their current Internet "address" since the stalker may take control of their machine. This allows another Internet-connected computer to recognise and establish a connection with a specific person's Windows-based machine. This "connection" is a computer-to-computer connection that enables the intruder to take control of the target's computer, not the link via a third party that characterises a usual Internet encounter. To carry out this type of Internet and Windows operating system exploitation, one currently needs a fair amount of computing expertise. On the Internet, though, are guidelines for use technology in this manner. Easier scripts will probably be made publicly available in the future for anybody who feels like downloading them.

1.4 Literature Review

A review of the literature not only makes the idea clearer, but it also makes it easier to understand so that repetition is avoided. It is really helpful in determining or recognising the issue. It aids in the formulation of the research approach as well. The written works It appears that a lot of research is being done on cyber-Stalking and its effects on society as a whole. Numerous research have attempted to ascertain whether existing regulations may be used to constrain the growing issue of cyber-stalking. The goal of the study was to learn how cyber-stalking is committed and how to stop it for the good of society.

- **Sukrut, Deo, Sapna, (2013),** "Cyberstalking & Online Harassment: A new challenge for law enforcement" The paper in Manupatra has studied various aspects of cyberstalking, right from what constitutes cyberstalking and online provocation, to how the nature of the internet as a medium encourages cyberstalking, similarities between cyberstalking and offline stalking and how online stalkers sense a false sense of security. The paper studies the current legislation in India in detail and also enforcement problems and finally provides prevention tips to avoid and remedies for internet users confronted with such behaviour.
- **Mishra, Alok, and Mishra, Deepti, (2008),** "Cyber Stalking: A Challenge for Web Security" The paper published in Research gate acknowledges that Cyberstalking is a nascent kind of crime that is becoming a global issue, though Cyber-terrorism might be taking priority in terms of action needed. The nature of the medium which offers anonymity has led to the rise in the number of cyberstalking; and technology available is yet to match the pace of the rise in cyberstalking. The chapter reviews endowment of legal acts. It analyses measures taken to prevent it across different geographies and also states that the legal acts are geographically limited, whereas the crime is not bounded by geographical limitations. It also emphasises the need to research various aspects of it.
- **Association for Progressive Communications (APC),** "Cyberstalking How to stay safe and protect yourself online" The study takes a closer look at various kinds of cyber stalkers and states that cyber stalkers can be strangers. They are also sometimes people we have known. It was also observed in the study, that as stalkers get more obsessive, they are likely to move across different channels and get information on the victim's location, personal and financial status apart from social and work life.
- **Hinduja, Sameer, Cyberstalking Research Centre,** "Cyberstalking" Harassment or stalking have existed earlier as well, what has newly emerged is the online dimension of it but the impacts are similar - annoyance, discomfort, sometimes leading to the extreme step of committing suicide. The study takes a closer look at the kinds of cyberstalking and feasible threats/risks that are possible including trauma caused by stealing somebody's identity or creating fake profiles etc. Along with different types of cyberstalking, the article also talks about preventive measures for cyberstalking and what can be done if you happen to be victimized by cyberstalking.
- **Criminology and Criminal Justice Senior Capstone, (2012),** "Prevention of Cyberstalking: A Review of the Literature Portland State University "The incidences of cyberstalking are increasing every year across the United States; the reasons can be attributed to a rise in technology and its users, thereby leading to the rise in the number of cyberstalking cases. The report explains the term cyberstalking, its prevalence among society, typical features of the people who fall victim to cyberstalking as well as offenders. The modus operandi of the crime is also explained. The study further explains the potential strategies to prevent cyberstalking which also includes giving necessary education about cyberstalking and changing internet behaviour.
- **Association for Progressive Communication, (2011),** "How to avoid becoming a cyberstalking victim" The paper published at Portland State University Library talks about various aspects of cyberstalking right from what is cyberstalking to how to prevent cyberstalking in the first place, and if still, one happens to fall victim to cyberstalking, then how can it be tackled

including details on how to file the complaint in case of being cyberstalked. It also gives tips to tackle cyberstalking, even for bloggers.

1.5 Objectives of the Study

The research/study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- To investigate the rising number of cybercrime incidents.
- To comprehend the definition, nature, and purpose of cyberstalking.
- To review the Indian legal system's legal provisions.
- To research the definition and kinds of cybercrime.
- To make recommendations for changes and corrective actions aimed at stopping and managing cyber-staking.
- To look into any potential flaws or gaps in the current cyber-Staking legislation and regulations.
- To examine Indian laws and regulations in order to stop and determine the beginnings and progression of cyber-staking.
- To research and evaluate criminal ideas via the lens of cyberstalking.
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1.6 Research Question

This study attempts to answer the followings questions:

- ❖ Does stalking under the USA and India's numerous penal laws, as well as the Information Technology Act of 2008, affect women and minors?
- ❖ What is cyber-Staking, and how are the different types of cyber-Staking?
- ❖ Is the Cyber Legislation in India effective and efficient enough for dealing with Cyber Staking in India?
- ❖ What is the demographic, social characteristics, and modus operandi of Cyber criminals?
- ❖ What should law enforcement agencies do for investigation and prosecution of cyber-Staking?
- ❖ What are the current Cyber Staking laws at national International Level?

1.7 Statement of the Problem

With digital technology, everyone has a place. This area, referred to as cyberspace, offers a distinct area for their operations. Almost every aspect of daily life involves the usage of the internet, including banking, communication, shopping, advertising, education, research, and entertainment. Hardly any activity is unaffected by the internet these days. In a nutshell, it may be claimed that humans have become infected by the Internet. Many young people have been found to have developed an addiction to being online all the time.

There is no denying that the development has accelerated due to internet technologies. Law enforcement organisations began working on the matter concurrently, but were unable and frustrated due to the unique characteristics of cyber-Staking. They discovered that they could not keep up with the rapidly advancing technologies. However, lawmakers also have to strike a balance between safeguarding the integrity of global public and private networks and upholding individual rights like free expression and privacy. Furthermore, law enforcement officers and investigating organisations use the same methods for gathering, reviewing, and assessing evidence when looking into cybercrimes as they do when looking into conventional crimes.

1.8 HYPOTHESIS

A problem cannot be scientifically solved unless it is reduced to hypothesis form. The word Hypothesis is the combination of two words Hypo + thesis. 'Hypo' refers to anything speculative or awaiting confirmation. "Thesis" refers to a logical argument on how to solve a certain issue. Hypothesis refers to an educated guess on how to solve the issue. A hypothesis outlines exactly what the researcher hopes to find out. When used properly, it may be an effective instrument for advancing knowledge since it is both compatible with current understanding and conducive to future investigation. For the uninitiated, it is a hypothesis whose veracity has not yet been established. Based on the assumption, it

may or may not be proved accurate since it is used as a guide for future research and to explain specific occurrences or phenomena.

In our nation, there is no comprehensive legislation that addresses cybercrimes. Nowadays, everyone can claim to be impacted by cybercrime since everyone is online—individuals, businesses, governments, and states. It has become a common demonology.

The goals of the legislation have not been met since the court system in our county does not support the effective enforcement of any law. Our legislature has not yet addressed the gravity of cybercrimes.

The breakthrough in computers and information technology has given civilization previously unheard-of benefits. People's lives have changed as a result of the internet's exponential expansion. Information technology is influencing every aspect of human endeavour, and it is bringing about global economic advancement and enormous benefits for all people. The illegal activity is not slowing down; all of a sudden, a new kind of criminal activity known as cybercrimes has emerged as a threat to society. The nation states are no longer able to observe this phenomenon in silence. Computer crime is far riskier than traditional crime in certain ways. It is hard to stop and simple to commit.

The researcher hopes to test the following hypothesis after the study to carry out this investigation:

1. There are no specific provisions in the Indian Penal Code, 1860, or the Information Technology Act, 2000 that address the problem of cyberstalking.
2. In India, there is no particular legislation against cyberstalking.
3. There is lack of awareness among Internet users about the proper cyber hygiene.
4. The existing legal mechanisms which are considered for Cyber Staking linked to women is not competent a sufficient amount to offer proficient treatments.
5. As Cyber Staking Can Be from Any Place but The Cases Are Unreported Due to Lack of International Jurisdiction.
6. There Is a Need of Amendment of Law as It Only Deals with The Staking Against Women and Not Men.

1.9 Research Methodology

Since this work is theological in nature, extensive research has been done in libraries. Both primary and secondary sources have provided the data and information.

Primary sources include the Constitution, Acts, Treaties, subordinate legislation, court and tribunal orders, and committee reports. For internal and external consistency, the cases rendered by different judicial and quasi-judicial forums have also been examined. Here, internal consistencies refer to how that specific issue is handled in different case scenarios, and external consistencies refer to how that issue is handled in relation to laws, regulations, etc. Secondary sources have included proceedings from national and international conferences on topics related to countering cyberterrorism. Secondary sources that address the topic include books, journals, articles, reports, and monographs. There have been numerous references to e-resources. Legal practises and other organisations have also provided assistance. Additionally, the beliefs, views, observations, and philosophies of.

Descriptive and qualitative research instruments have been used in doctrinal studies. In order to learn more about anecdotal incidents, institutional operations, and group behaviour patterns, descriptive studies have been conducted. It has been used to comprehend research issues. The aim of this study was to improve predictability in specific situations. Qualitative research has been utilised for case analysis and system comparison studies.

The information gathered from primary and secondary sources has been presented in a detailed way, with essential contributions added where needed.

The study has employed empirical evidence from primary and secondary sources, although being essentially a doctrinal one. Nevertheless, neither a field investigation nor the formal interview or questionnaire methods of data gathering were used. The work does not acknowledge the numerous informal talks with numerous subject matter experts because all points are supported by published materials. Secondary sources were utilised in order to understand the statute.

The current analysis likewise has foreign legislation as its foundation. To have a better knowledge of the various provisions of Indian legislation, comparative studies of the laws of the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Japan, and Australia were also conducted.

A crime will be committed in the current work, "THE LEGAL DIMENSION OF CYBER STALKING IN INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY." The information of individuals, businesses, societies, or governments is the target of almost all cybercrime. Cybercrime is the most recent and possibly most challenging issue in the cyber world. Technology is used by criminals to carry out these crimes. Cyberstalking is one of these, which is the practise of following someone using electronic mail. Cyberstalking is the practise of a stalker persistently attempting to get in touch with someone else with the aim of controlling their lives or making them fearful. A cyber-stalker has replaced the conventional stalker. Additionally, because of advancements in information technology, stalkers can now conceal their identities, allowing them to conduct crimes anonymously while remaining comfortably indoors.

Cyber stalking shares many of the same harassment principles as traditional stalking; however, the victims are mostly located on the internet. Cyberstalking attempts are most commonly made via chat rooms, emails, the internet, and the newly popular social networks like Facebook. Numerous investigators have found that. Victims of cyberstalking might be either men or women. Under Indian law, the term "cybercrime" lacks a precise definition. In actuality, the Indian Penal Code never uses the term "cybercrime," even after it was modified by the Information Technology (Amendment) Act of 2008.

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Address of related Website:

In this study, many websites will be used for the purpose of data collection. Some of important websites are:

- <http://WWW.shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>
- <http://WWW.legal-articles.deysot.com>
- <http://WWW.indiakanoon.org>
- <http://WWW.Indialawjournal.com>
- <http://WWW.lawmin.nic.in>
- <http://WWW.indiacode.nic.in>
- <http://WWW.NCRB.nic.in>
- <http://www.cyberlawtimes.com/articles/103.html>

